

Data management plan for Nr. LU-BA-ZG-2024/1-0020 Project title: The new paradigm in education – changing values and integrating Sustainable Development goals into the study content New

Version 1

Description

Project Abstract: “Sustainability science is the science of sustainability to understand how complex physical, biological and social systems work; and it is the science of sustainability to support sustainable policy and positive social change.” (UNESCO)

Sustainable development is a basic condition that affects the Latvian economy, the education system and also the activities of the University of Latvia - education, research, organizational development and external contacts. Education ensures the acquisition of knowledge, skills and competencies for students to be able to solve problems, taking into account the context of sustainable development. Science-based research is critical to providing an understanding of known or currently unknown future problems.

The relevance of the analysis of the United Nations (UN) Sustainable Development Goals is based on the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development.

This interdisciplinary research project will contribute to the implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals in study programs. The project will develop recommendations for the quality management/regulation of education and scientific research systems based on the goals of Sustainable Development, to ensure research-based studies and connections with industries through the study process, and various study courses.

Keywords: Sustainability science; Sustainable Development Goals; understanding and changing values; study content; Social sciences

Funder

European Commission | | EC

Grant

Recovery and Resilience Facility
project Internal and External
Consolidation of the University
of Latvia(No.
5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007)

Researchers

Dzintra Atstaja (orcid:0000-0002-9411-7212)

Organizations

BA School of Business and Finance

1. Main Info

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Organizations:

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: European Commission | EC

Grants: Recovery and Resilience Facility project Internal and External Consolidation of the University of Latvia(No. 5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007)

Project: The new Paradigm in Education – Changing Values and integrating Sustainable Development Goals into the study content (LU-BA-ZG-2024/1-0020)

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

Publication Date:

4. Templates

Descriptions

Focus group and Experts interviews - discussion minutes

Focus group interviews - discussion minutes, data, place and members,

to organize discussion groups: for in-depth study of the understanding of students in universities and colleges about the understanding of Sustainable Development goals in connection with the topics of qualifications and study courses

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

Data Management Plan | Data management plan for Nr. LU-BA-ZG-2024/1-0020 Project title: The new paradigm in education – changing values and integrating Sustainable Development goals into the study content New LICENSE:CC-BY-4.0 DOI: - 19/09/2025

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Data collection aims to analyze understanding and needs in the Latvian education system. Exchanging Information and Gathering Expert Opinions.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- PDF

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

a. 50

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

no similar data available

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

for researchers and scientists of social sciences

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

Grammarly

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

Yes

Rayyan

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

No

2.1.7 Other relevant remarks

Expert interviews:

1) Expert interview guidelines (in LATVIAN);

2) Transcripts of Experts interviews (AI-generated in Microsoft 365's Ecosystem from voice/ video recording). 17 pdf files - one per each Expert interview (in LATVIAN).

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1HI22s82jKPRKAJwXVEU9uP0XiWwvrXFc?usp=drive_link

Qualitative study. Focus group discussions:

1) Discussion guidelines (in LATVIAN);

2) Transcripts of Focus group discussions. 3 PDF files - one for each discussion (in LATVIAN);

3) Methodology of Qualitative study (in LATVIAN);

4) Report of qualitative study (in LATVIAN);

5) Summary of qualitative study (in ENGLISH);

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1IU9WAojjTPlo1vRM5nUNXBqegKSrTWz9?usp=drive_link

Quantitative study:

1) Data file. 3 CVS files (in LATVIAN);

2) Tables of results (in LATVIAN);

3) Description of methodology (in LATVIAN);

4) Quantitative study questionnaire (in LATVIAN and ENGLISH);

5) Report of quantitative study (in ENGLISH);

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1pk7pjRfapXDGttS4K586-vOSP4fvyVIU?usp=drive_link

Students' applied research:

1) Report (in LATVIAN)

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1vpZxphDwNBg5rriMGC0q6wdX-T-gK67Y?usp=drive_link

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

No

Zenodo.org

Microsoft

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

word doc

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2025-01-10

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

the data remains re-usable as needed, depending on demand

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Dzintra Atstaja (orcid: [0000-0002-9411-7212](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9411-7212))

Risk prevention will be ensured during the project through the following measures: (1) providing a clear and detailed description of the project; (2) involving a scientific assistant in the controlling schedule; (3) ensuring full transparency for the duration of the project for stakeholders and interests. The Project Manager will continuously update potential new risks, evaluating their risk and defining the risk treatment measures. The role of the scientific assistant will be to engage in the organization of day-to-day activities, including implementing quality control measures. The Project manager handles the Risk management.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

no additional costs are planned

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Passwords

Data storage in the university file cloud

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.5 If yes, what are the methods used to process and access personal data/sensitive information

Anonymising data

The expert's name and occupation will only be disclosed with his consent.

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